

The Communication Interpersonal Efforts of Kindergarten Teacher in Overcoming Learning Loss During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Kabupaten Tangerang

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the interpersonal communication efforts of kindergarten teachers and the communication barriers faced to overcome learning loss during the Covid-19 pandemic in Kabupaten Tangerang. The method used in this study is a qualitative method and the analytical technique used is the Miles and Huberman interactive model technique through interviews, documentation and observation. The subjects of this research include teachers and school principals in Kabupaten Tangerang. The results of data analysis show that 1) learning conditions during the Covid-19 pandemic are limited through online and offline (2) Kindergarten teacher interpersonal communication efforts during the Covid-19 pandemic. (3) communication barriers faced by kindergarten teachers when building interpersonal communication with their students. This research is expected to be a reference for other parties, especially students of the educational communication program to develop interpersonal communication between teachers and students.

Keywords:- *Kindergarten Teacher, Interpersonal Communication, Learning Loss.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A good education will pay attention to a task and the role of the teacher in improving student competence. The communication skills of a teacher are needed to achieve the competence of these students. This requires a teacher to have communication skills in conveying their roles and duties. One of the communication skill that must be developed is interpersonal communication. Interpersonal communication according to Devito (2016) is communication that exists between people who are connected to each other. it can occur between children and their parents, teachers and students, a leader and his subordinates and so on. Interpersonal communication also has the impact each other. Warsita (2014) said that Interpersonal communication can be done face-to-face directly or through a media reveals that interpersonal communication can be done face-to-face or using electronic communication media such as email, social media, telephone, video conference and online tutorials. This communication process can occur reciprocally directly (synchronous) at that time or require response time at a later time (asynchronous).

Interpersonal communication of a teacher has an influence on learning behavior and student achievement as research conducted by Fathurohman (2018) that interpersonal communication between teachers and students has a positive and significant influence. This affects students' motivation in learning. As a study conducted by Malik (2014) that in the learning process it is very necessary to have good communication between teachers and students in terms of not only transferring knowledge but also creating a better education. This is in line with the communication principle expressed by Devito (2016), offline or online interpersonal has five main objectives, namely interpersonal communication for learning, creating relationships, influencing, helping and playing.

The ability to communicate interpersonally must be absolutely possessed by an educator in socializing with their environment. According to Akhtim's statement in simorangkir (2019) that as a social being, interpersonal communication skills are very important. But sometimes, it is difficult for an educator to do this because it is caused by several factors including fear, lack of confidence, feeling neglected when teachers interact to the students. So, the teacher's interpersonal communication should be improved as an interaction way to the students.

However, due to the Covid-19 pandemic that has occurred since the end of 2019 has created own phenomenon for the education. The government through Surat Keputusan Bersama (SKB) Empat Menteri in 2020 caused the limitation of social interaction as an effort to minimize the spread of the Covid-19 virus. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture, Research and Technology (2020) there are hundreds of schools closed and around 68 million students studying from home, and around four million teachers conducting distance teaching activities.

The existence of the limitation of social interaction makes students have on learning problems and increasing boredom. This causes a decrease in learning understanding or what is called learning loss. According to the Education and Development Forum (2020) learning loss is a condition in which students lose knowledge academically due to the lack of instructional process. As a result, student competence and learning experienced significantly decline.

During pandemic Covid-19, students experience a lack of direct interaction caused by distance learning. It makes the students character development and soft skills are reduced. Furthermore, the process of interaction and activities with teachers and friends at school is also reduced. So, it can decrease in learning understanding (learning loss).

Learning loss is a decrease in understanding in learning caused by the cessation of the learning process due to a disaster. According to The Education and Development Forum in 2020, it means that learning loss is a situation for students to lose knowledge and skills academically due to a prolonged gap in the learning process. Meanwhile, the risk of learning loss has been predicted by several world organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF, WORLD BANK in April 2020 stating that global school closures will cause a decrease in understanding in learning. Furthermore, Donnelly & Patrinos stated that the situation of learning loss was influenced by the unpreparedness of teachers and school administration to face the transition and distance learning system. The term learning loss arises because of a decrease in the value of students' knowledge and skills when measured through a test and the results are reduced from previous years.

The Covid-19 pandemic has caused the closure of face-to-face learning in schools throughout Indonesia since its emergence. Many schools in Indonesia make distance learning mechanisms or online learning, but this does not work effectively because there are many obstacles that occur in the implementation process. Among the obstacles that occur are the lack of digital skills possessed by students and teachers in online learning, inadequate internet access, and lack of parental assistance. As data released by the World Bank states that the Covid-19 pandemic has caused the closure of several schools in Indonesia and forced 68 million children to study online at home, but with varying access and absorption among students affected by online learning.

The World Bank in its report entitled "Estimate of Covid-19 Impacts on Learning and Earning and How to Turn the Tide" stated that the estimated decline in learning understanding caused by learning restrictions due to the Covid-19 pandemic resulted in a large impact in the future. One of the analyzes is that students who lose learning opportunities due to the Covid-19 pandemic will lose an income of around 13.5 percent of Indonesia's 2019 GDP or around US\$ 249, US\$ 367, or US\$ 484 using the level of the US dollar purchasing power equation. (PPP) 2017. Learning is closely related to student income in the future because education makes workers more productive and skilled. The World Bank also emphasized that Indonesia is similar to most other countries which are less prepared to manage the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, thus causing a negative impact on student learning outcomes both now and in the future.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used in this study is a qualitative method. The subjects selected in this study were two kindergarten teachers and one principal from three schools representing Kabupaten Tangerang, namely Indria Islamic School, Sepatan, Al-Fajar Islamic Kindergarten, Kosambi and Kelapa Dua Islamic Village Kindergarten.

Meanwhile, the data collecting techniques in this study used:

A. Interviews

Qualitative interviews were conducted to obtain data sources from participants through unstructured or open-ended questions. This is done to get a comprehensive view or perspective from the participants.

B. Observations

Observations were made by researchers going directly to the field to examine the behavior and activities of participants at the research site. In the process of direct observation, researchers recorded both structured and unstructured behavior or activities of participants.

C. Documentations

Documentation is used to help researchers collect various research data to support maximum results. This documentation can be taken from participants' personal documents or photos of participants in their activities and behavior.

Whereas, the data analysis techniques follow the interactive analysis model expressed by Miles and Huberman (1992) namely data collection, data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interpersonal communication between teachers and kindergarten students is needed in building closeness. Interpersonal communication skills must be possessed by teachers to understand the students' character and abilities. In addition, interpersonal communication skills are used to avoid miss communication that occurs between teachers and students.

A concept by Devito (2016) which states that to establish an effective interpersonal communication must have the following five concepts, namely openness, empathy, support, positive attitude and equality. This concept is also carried out by a kindergarten teacher in establishing a good relationship with students. For example, openness and empathy are built to make comfort zone and trust each other. The openness, empathy, equality, support, and a positive feeling are needed in building interpersonal communication in instructional process.

Kindergarten teachers' interpersonal communication serves as a guide in learning, conveys information and supervises educational activities. It is including openness, empathy, positive attitude, support and equality in order to create a good interpersonal communication. Through an interview with several kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang that every teacher must have good communication skills, especially when they build an interpersonal communication with kindergarten students. The Effective communication will affect kindergarten teachers in establishing a closeness with their students.

A. The Efforts to Build Interpersonal Communication Between Kindergarten Teachers and Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic to Overcome Learning Loss in Kabupaten Tangerang

The efforts made by kindergarten teachers to create effective interpersonal communication is to establish a good relationship between teachers and kindergarten students. It is to be place student feel free to share, argue, and convey their ideas comfortably and safely. It will be the deep bounding each other so that transferring learning messages will be easier. Interpersonal communication efforts between teachers and students are usually carried out in two directions, built a trust, touch and gesture. Interpersonal communication efforts usually begin with understanding the students' personality and character.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, where restrictions on social interaction were limited, the direct communication process was also limited. It is affects the direct communication between teachers and kindergarten students limited. On the one hand, all programs that have been designed by schools must continue to run. On the other hand, schools must also comply with government policies to carry out social restrictions. Furthermore, this social restriction causes a lack of interaction between teachers and students so that the delivery of learning motivation is not conveyed properly. This phenomenon encourages every school to carry out blended learning, namely activities in the network (online) and outside the network (offline). Online and offline methods are carried out so that the learning and communication process continues as it should. Blended learning is deemed necessary so that students feel stuck in the learning process. This is where the role of interpersonal communication continues to run.

The learning process in schools, especially in kindergarten schools in Kabupaten Tangerang has also undergone changes. Effective interpersonal communication is still built so that there is no decrease in learning understanding in kindergarten students even though it is done virtually or through zoom media, google meet or WhatsApp video calls.

Furthermore, the impact of learning during the pandemic is felt by teachers and students, especially on the lack of communication interaction. Whereas communication between teachers and kindergarten students must continue to be established an effective communication. Kindergarten teachers are very aware of this situation, so the school has started to implement policies that are considered as a

substitute for learning activities in schools even though they are carried out virtually. This is expected to be able to establish interpersonal communication between students and teachers effectively so that learning objectives can still be achieved.

The following are the interpersonal communication efforts made by kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang in overcoming learning loss, namely with kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang conducting interpersonal communication effectively. From the research results of Kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang, it shows that:

- Kindergarten teachers conduct interpersonal communication effectively and promote openness as a way to get close to their students. The teachers make new students feel comfortable and safe to be able to communicate and interact.
- Empathy is also shown by a kindergarten teacher to be able to enter into a kindergarten student. So that Kindergarten teachers are able to explore the characters that exist in students.
- Support or a supportive attitude will understand the feelings of others. This is also done by kindergarten teachers conveying any support to students in terms of activities and attitudes.
- Positive feelings given between the communicator and the communicant in the interpersonal communication process will provide a good assessment and create a pleasant atmosphere. Kindergarten teachers will build a positive atmosphere in order to create a conducive atmosphere.
- Equality will override social status, power, property and intellectuality. A kindergarten teacher does not discriminate between one student and another. This will provide an equal and equal.
- Kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang continue to carry out interpersonal communication virtually for that in learning during the Covid-19 period, a kindergarten teacher must continue to carry out interpersonal communication with their students so that interactions occur in the learning delivery process such as using various existing digital platforms.

B. The Obstacle to Interpersonal Communication of Teachers and Students during the Covid-19 Pandemic in Kabupaten Tangerang

The obstacles faced by Kindergarten teachers usually come from the personality of the students themselves. Some students who do not want to communicate interpersonally because they have their own trauma or difficult to open up with new people. Communication barriers usually occur in new kindergarten students who experience psychological barriers due to characters brought from home. Then, the obstacles that occur in the process of interpersonal communication can cause disruption of the message delivery process. For this reason, the obstacles that occur can be summarized into:

a) Technical Obstacle

Technical barriers occur when a message that is conveyed has a problem with the media so that the process of delivering the message experiences problems. An example of a technical obstacle in communication is a disturbance in the transmission device that is damaged so that the process of delivering messages online is experiencing obstacles. This happens when interpersonal communication between teachers and kindergarten students is carried out through digital media such as zoom, google meet and video calls which are constrained by the internet network.

b) Psychological Obstacle

Psychological barriers are obstacles that occur in individuals who are involved in interpersonal communication such as anger, grief, suspicion or sadness. This will affect the imperfection of the message delivery process. This happens when the beginning of the new school year is constrained by the initial character of students who are not yet known by the teachers.

c) Semantic Obstacle

Namely barriers that arise due to the language used in the process of delivering messages. For example, when the language used is understood or has a different meaning for the communicant, it will lead to misperceptions or misunderstandings, then this becomes an obstacle in the process of delivering messages. Barriers like this usually occur in kindergarten students who have a different language and culture from the teacher so that at the beginning of the introduction they experience problems when building effective interpersonal communication.

From the description above, the obstacles that occur in the interpersonal communication process can cause disruption of the message delivery process. These obstacles usually occur at the beginning of its implementation, but when an interpersonal communication and interaction relationship is running smoothly, these obstacles can be easily overcome. After a communication has been well established through efforts to create effective communication, the communication must be maintained even in a pandemic.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Kindergarten teachers' interpersonal communication skills are needed for an approach to kindergarten students to convey information, learning targets and personal closeness in understanding students' characters. Interpersonal communication can be built into an effective communication through an approach between teachers and kindergarten students during the learning process both online and offline. Interpersonal communication skills can be realized by building openness, empathy, support, a sense of positivity and equality between teachers and kindergarten students.

The learning process at Kindergarten in Kabupaten Tangerang during the Covid-19 pandemic was carried out using online and offline methods. The online method is carried out using digital platforms such as zoom meetings, google meet, WhatsApp video calls, and WhatsApp voice

notes. The obstacles faced in building interpersonal communication between teachers and students occur because of technical, psychological, and semantic constraints.

Based on the conclusions that have been described previously, there are suggestions for improving interpersonal communication for kindergarten teachers in Kabupaten Tangerang in particular and kindergarten teachers in Indonesia in general. The suggestions are that Kindergarten teachers should have good communication skills as an effort to establish a good interaction relationship between teachers and students and various digital media such as zoom meetings, google meet, WhatsApp video calls and so on can be used as a medium to continue to establish communication interpersonal relationships between teachers and students. Meanwhile, for further researchers, they can conduct. Research with subjects and research objects at a higher age level such as interpersonal communication for elementary, junior high, and high school teachers both in Kabupaten Tangerang and in other areas

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